

Bringing the Service Perspective to Understand Customer Engagement and Value Co-creation with Smart Energy Services

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1. INTRODUCTION

Customer engagement with smart energy services is a priority for the European Union, and its main research and innovation focus is on the areas of smart service design and active customer engagement [1], as smart grids are deeply changing the paradigm of energy production and consumption [2]. However, the energy sector is facing challenges in the process of deployment of this technology at the low and medium voltage levels, due to the lack of customer engagement with energy services [3], representing a huge barrier to adoption. Hence, more research is required to meet this challenge, in order to generate relevant inputs for the development of new smart energy services [4], which encompasses the integration of new actors in this new ecosystem to co-create value within a multistakeholder service network [5]. In this context, the holistic nature of services brings contributions to understand and foster customer engagement with smart energy services, having the co-creation of value as an outcome. From the service perspective, customers are active co-creators of value, and service is an enabler of value co-creation, together with other resources in the customer value network [6]. Additionally, customer engagement is defined as a psychological state that occurs in the function of interactions in co-creative customer experiences in particular service relationships [7]. Both perspectives, emphasize customers' contributions to interactional and co-creative of value processes, network centered and, thus, inherently relational [8].

This paper integrates smart grid and service perspectives to understand the role of customer engagement with smart energy services and, how value is co-created through this. The study consisted of a qualitative study covering customers of home energy management systems (HEMS), electric vehicle (EV) customers and residential customers with high consumption of electricity. The study has been developed in a European project H2020 in partnership with a Portuguese energy company and the Faculty of Engineering of the University of Porto.

2. EMPIRICAL STUDY AND RESULTS

The study involved focus groups and in-depth interviews with a total of 31 participants covering three groups: customers of Home Energy Management Systems (HEMS) (11), electric vehicle (EV) customers (10) and residential customers with high consumption of electricity (10). These groups were selected as they adopt different roles in the smart energy service ecosystem and different levels of proactivity regarding the service offering. A partner utility company from the European project consortium provided the sample of customers of HEMS and high consumption and EV customers were recruited in social media.

Study results showed that these three groups present different levels of customer engagement and are motivated by different value co-creation goals. HEMS customers, as early adopters, are independent, meaning that they implement the system on their own or they can eventually hire a full-service to support their daily activities. They are well informed and are willing to control and manage energy consumption to achieve their main goals - savings and energy efficiency. EV customers are proactive and part of a large community that shares daily experiences of use, besides management and functionalities issues that are not available in manufacturers' information channels. The daily activity plans of the car are based on the community inputs and support services, as such, application data and websites. EV's are important ecosystem components, as they consume a significant part of

the house energy, pushing the customer to take decisions regarding the charging routine in off-peak periods or use public stations, and set arrangements in home electrical installation. Additionally, the car battery can be useful to support the energy customer to manage the power supply of a house during the night. Residential customers with high consumption of electricity are not aware of smart grids technology or smart energy services, therefore they are not advanced or independent users as the other groups. However, they showed interest in full-service value propositions that provide the benefits, but not the hassle of adopting a new mindset and behavior regarding energy consumption. These results also provide useful insights for energy service providers to engage and co-create value with these different groups of customers. In case of HEMS customers and EV customers, they want to be in control of their consumption decisions. In this context, smart service providers and customers should offer a value proposition that enables them to interact in real-time to adjust dynamically their demand, pushing operators to adjust their procedures and resources to offer the service efficiently. On the other hand, residential customers with high consumption of electricity do not necessarily want to assume active roles in service provision. Energy service providers have the opportunity to develop a full service for these customers that reap the benefits of smart energy services. In this case, service providers can operate based on forecasts over time, adjusting their operations accordingly.

4. CONCLUSION

This study brings a service perspective and shows how it can contribute with solutions for engaging customers with smart energy services, taking into account value co-creation as a relevant outcome in this process. Based on the results of the empirical study, customers wish to play different roles to co-create value and reap benefits from the grid, and not all of them want to play an active role. In this context, full-service offerings can engage these customers by understanding how they respond to different interactions and relationships in the service network according to their goals towards energy consumption and management. These results highlight the need to focus on value co-creation with customers and other actors in the value network, in which customer engagement plays a crucial role to achieve the final goals.

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